
TOWARDS VICTORY: STRATEGIES TO BECOME A POKER CHAMPION

[Edição 122 MAI/23 SUMÁRIO, Linguística, Letras e Artes / 01/05/2023](#)

REGISTRO DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10719940

Teddy Lyncoln Tavares Correa¹

Poker is more than just a card game. It's an arena where skill, strategy, and intuition collide, and where players from around the world compete for prestige, fame, and fortune. In this article, we will explore not only the strategies necessary to become a poker champion, but also the history of the game, its current market, and its influence on the world.

History of Poker:

Poker has a rich history dating back to the 18th century, with its roots in French and German card games. Over the centuries, the game has evolved and spread around the world, adopting different variants and styles of play along the way. In the 20th century, poker gained popularity in the United States, especially in saloons and casinos in Las Vegas, becoming a symbol of American culture.

Poker Market:

Today, poker is a global multi-billion dollar market, with millions of players participating in live and online tournaments worldwide. Major events

such as the World Series of Poker (WSOP) and the World Poker Tour (WPT) attract elite players and offer impressive cash prizes. Additionally, online poker has exploded in popularity, providing easy access to the game for millions of players worldwide.²

According to recent statistics, the global poker market generated approximately \$15 billion in revenue in 2021, with growth forecasted for the coming years. Furthermore, online poker experienced a significant increase in demand during the COVID-19 pandemic, with a 40% increase in player traffic on some platforms.

Impact on the World:

Poker is not just a game, but also a global community of passionate players and dedicated professionals. In addition to its influence on the world of entertainment and business, poker also has a significant impact on popular culture, inspiring movies, books, and television shows. Moreover, poker promotes skills such as strategic reasoning, decision-making under pressure, and bankroll management, which can be applied in other areas of life.

How to use bet blocker Take the lead, be the aggressor and crush your opponents by making bet after bet. That's the way to win at no-limit hold'em, right? Except it's not always that easy, right? Sometimes you have a hand that is just average. You think you're the best at the table, but you don't want to risk a big bet. In this situation, the best form of attack is often defense. Welcome to the world of blocker betting. Making a small bet can prevent your opponent from making you bet bigger than you wanted and also take some extra value from an opponent with a weak hand who wouldn't make a big bet. Big warning: These bets may not be profitable against strong and aggressive opponents. Good players can detect a small bet on the river as a sign of weakness. In general, it's okay to make blocking bets until you play against mid-stakes players willing to take big risks. Your blocking bets should be smaller than your value bets

(30% of the pot should do the job)³. When to use In a 1v1 pot, when you have the lead throughout the hand and reach the river with a weak advantage. Avoid being pressured into a big bet or folding with a blocker bet When you are on a reasonable draw. A defensive bet here can confuse your opponent and prevent you from being cornered. On the turn, to prevent your opponent at them with value bets to make them make this crucial mistake. The guy with the big pot. This player will simply always re-raise you. Limp (pay the blind amount) after the flop and get into position for a pot that isn't worth stealing, but is worth having. These players are perfect for winning after the flop, as they have no idea what to do from there. In the middle and late stages of the tournament, remember that some players are short on chips and desperate. As you approach the bubble, you should have a good chance of playing small ball against the player who really wants to win some money. Against everyone else, be ready to adjust. When not to play small ball When you're sitting at the big dog table and you're ready to go with a good hand. Play big, raise big, and force them to put money in before they want to.

Conclusion:

Poker is a fascinating game that goes beyond cards and chips. It's a journey of selfimprovement, competition, and camaraderie that attracts players from all backgrounds and ages. If you're looking to become a poker champion, remember to study, practice, and never stop learning. With determination and dedication, you can achieve great success at the poker tables and leave your mark on the exciting world of the world's most popular card game.

²https://medium.com/@abhishek.singh_27347/poker-pros-masters-of-the-cards-and-the-mind-32815b1a67b23- Poker Movies and Pop Culture – GGPoker

¹Teddy Lincoln Tavares Correa é um engenheiro de produção e campeão de poker do Rio de Janeiro. Graduado na Faculdade FAESA, ele se destacou em sua carreira profissional e no poker. Teddy tornou-se Campeão Paulista de Poker, exibindo habilidades estratégicas e determinação excepcionais. Sua história inspiradora ilustra a combinação única de sucesso nas mesas de poker e no mundo corporativo

[← Post anterior](#)

[Post seguinte →](#)

RevistaFT

A RevistaFT têm 28 anos. É uma **Revista Científica Eletrônica Multidisciplinar Indexada de Alto Impacto e Qualis “B2”**.

Periodicidade mensal e de acesso livre. Leia gratuitamente todos os artigos e publique o seu também [clikando aqui](#).

Contato

Queremos te ouvir.

WhatsApp RJ:

(21) 98159-7352

WhatsApp SP:

(11) 98597-3405

e-Mail:

contato@revistaf
t.com.br

ISSN: 1678-0817

CNPJ:

48.728.404/0001-
22

**FI= 5.397 (muito
alto)**

Fator de impacto é um método bibliométrico para avaliar a

Conselho Editorial

Editores

Fundadores:

Dr. Oston de Lacerda Mendes.
Dr. João Marcelo Gigliotti.

Editor

Científico:

Dr. Oston de Lacerda Mendes

Orientadoras:

Dra. Hevellyn Andrade Monteiro

Dra. Chimene Kuhn Nobre

Revisores:

Lista atualizada

importância de periódicos científicos em suas respectivas áreas. Uma medida que reflete o número médio de citações de artigos científicos publicados em determinado periódico, criado por Eugene Garfield, em que os de maior FI são considerados mais importantes.

periodicamente em revistaft.com.br/expandente. Venha fazer parte de nosso time de revisores também!